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THE INFLUENCE OF COMMUNICATION AND JOB CHARACTERISTICS ON EMPLOYEE PERFORMANCE THROUGH MOTIVATION AS AN INTERVENING VARIABLE IN BADAN PENDAPATAN DAERAH KABUPATEN LABUHAN BATU

ВПЛИВ КОМУНІКАЦІЇ ТА ХАРАКТЕРИСТИК РОБОТИ НА ПРОДУКТИВНІСТЬ ПРАЦІВНИКІВ ЧЕРЕЗ МОТИВАЦІЮ ЯК ПРОМІЖНУ ЗМІННУ В РЕГІОНАЛЬНОМУ АГЕНТСТВІ ДОХОДІВ ОКРУГУ ЛАБУХАН-БАТУ

Bambang Suwarno
University of Prima Indonesia, Medan, Indonesia
ORCID: 0000-0002-9563-7287

Fajar Rezeki Ananda Lubis
University of Prima Indonesia, Medan, Indonesia
ORCID: 0009-0006-0971-3025

Dahnil Anzar Simanjuntak
University of Prima Indonesia, Medan, Indonesia
ORCID: 0009-0009-9973-5704

Melfrianti Romauli Purba
University of Prima Indonesia, Medan, Indonesia
ORCID: 0000-0002-5956-616X

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Бамбанг Суварно, Фаджар Резекі Анада Лубіс, Дахніл Анзар Сіманджунтак, Мелфріанті Ромаулі Пурба. Вплив комунікації та характеристик роботи на продуктивність працівників через мотивацію як проміжну змінну в Регіональному агентстві доходів округу Лабухан-Бату. Науково-методична стаття.

Дослідження спрямоване на визначення впливу комунікації та характеристик роботи на результативність працівників через мотивацію як посередницьку змінну в Регіональному агентстві доходів округу Лабуханбату. У дослідженні взяли участь усі 57 постійних державних службовців (PNS), застосовано метод суцільної вибірки. Дані збиралися за допомогою анкетування та аналізу документації. Кількісний аналіз проводився з використанням SPSS версії 25, зокрема t-тесту, тесту Собея та шляхового аналізу. Результати свідчать, що комунікація та характеристики роботи мають позитивний і статистично значущий вплив на мотивацію та результативність праці. Мотивація також позитивно впливає на результативність і виступає ефективною посередницькою змінною.

Ключові слова: характеристики роботи, продуктивність, комунікація та мотивація

Bambang Suwarno, Fajar Rezeki Ananda Lubis, Dahnil Anzar Simanjuntak, Melfrianti Romauli Purba. The Influence of Communication and Job Characteristics on Employee Performance Through Motivation as an Intervening Variable in Badan Pendapatan Daerah Kabupaten Labuhan Batu. Scientific and methodical article.

This study examines the effect of Communication and Job Characteristics on Employee Performance through Motivation as an intervening variable at the Regional Revenue Agency of Labuhanbatu Regency. The study involved all 57 permanent civil servants (PNS), using a saturated sampling technique. Data were collected through questionnaires and documentation. Quantitative analysis was conducted using SPSS version 25, including t-tests, Sobel tests, and path analysis. The results show that Communication and Job Characteristics have a positive and significant effect on Motivation and Performance. Motivation also has a positive and significant effect on Performance and acts as an effective mediating variable between Communication, Job Characteristics, and Performance.

Keywords: job characteristics, performance, communication and motivation

One of the important components of management is human resources (HR), because humans are the main and important assets as the driving force and regulator of a company or organization. To achieve goals according to the vision and mission that have been set by the organization, it is very dependent on the individual/human. Every organization or company will always strive to improve employee performance, because improving performance is an important program in an organization or company because performance greatly affects the success of an organization or company (Ramadhan, MS, et al. 2022).

Analysis of recent research and publications

The Labuhanbatu Regency Revenue Agency performs supporting functions for the government in the area of regional revenue. The Labuhanbatu Regency Revenue Agency is a local government agency that continuously strives to improve the quality of its human resources through training, training, technical guidance, and benchmarking or exchange of experiences with other regions in Indonesia. This is expected to enhance understanding and ultimately enable the agency to conduct public awareness campaigns to increase public awareness in the field of taxation and fees, both related to corporate/business taxes and individual taxes, which are technically regulated by existing regulations.

In order to achieve its objectives, it will require the support of responsible, dedicated, and highly professional human resources with integrity from each personnel member. In addition, it will also be supported by human resource management to manage all human resources within the agency.

In an initial survey conducted by researchers, the performance of employees at the Labuhanbatu District Revenue Agency was found to be suboptimal. This certainly has implications for the overall performance of the Labuhanbatu District Revenue Agency. Improved performance is highly desirable in order to boost revenue for the Labuhanbatu District.

The work process will ultimately result in employee performance that is in line with the company's objectives. Whether in the context of a manufacturing or service company, employee performance is very important in measuring the success of the organization. High work motivation encourages employees to contribute maximally in carrying out their duties, while low motivation can result in a lack of enthusiasm and a tendency to give up easily. Job characteristics aim to organize assignments that meet the needs of the organization, technological aspects, and individual behavior. Job characteristics are descriptions that serve as guidelines for task execution, which in turn can increase job satisfaction. Employee performance can improve thanks to managers' understanding of job characteristics, enabling them to assign diverse and more demanding tasks.

The main part

According to Torang (2014), performance is the quantity or quality of work output of individuals or groups within an organization when carrying out their main tasks and functions, based on norms, standard operating procedures, and criteria and measures that have been established or are applicable within the organization.

Performance is about the results of a series of jobs achieved during a certain period of time and can be measured in terms of quality and quantity with the aim of assessing the suitability of work with the goals to be achieved in the organization. According to Nurjaya (2021) indicators that can measure performance are as follows:

1. Quantity of work results.
2. Quality of work results.
3. Efficiency.
4. Work discipline.
5. Initiative.
6. Accuracy.
7. Leadership.
8. Honesty.
9. Creativity.

According to Agus M. Hardjana (2016), communication is an activity in which individuals convey messages through certain media to others, and after receiving the message, they respond to the sender.

According to Andrew E. Sikula (2017), "Communication is a process of transferring information, understanding, and knowledge from

individuals, locations, or entities to other individuals, locations, or entities".

Communication is an activity of conveying concepts or ideas that are in our minds and the desires that we want to convey to others with the aim of providing information or understanding. According to Sutardji (2016) there are several indicators of effective communication, namely as follows:

1. Understanding.
2. Pleasure.
3. Influence on attitude.
4. The relationship is getting better.
5. Action.

According to Stoner and Freeman in Sumarsono (2014), "Job characteristics are attributes of an employee's tasks that include various types of responsibilities and the level of satisfaction derived from those characteristics". According to Jatmiko (2011), "Job characteristics indicate the extent to which employees have authority in making decisions related to their work and how many tasks employees must complete".

Job Characteristics are the nature and tasks that show how a job is described in detail for each worker, such as clarity of tasks, authority, responsibility, procedures, and feedback. In addition, Job Characteristics are also different properties between one type of job and another in its implementation. According to Hackman and Oldham (1975), Job Characteristics have the following indicators:

1. Skill variation.
2. Task identification.
3. Significance of the task.
4. Autonomy.
5. Feedback.

Motivation is an intrinsic drive that encourages individuals to act or behave, referring to the origin of behavior that triggers a person to do or avoid something. Motivation can also be understood as the desire to achieve a higher degree in the life of each individual.

According to Sinungan (2016), "Motivation is a psychological condition and mental attitude of an individual that provides encouragement, directs activities or movements, and channels behavior toward the achievement of needs that provide satisfaction or reduce imbalance."

This is indicated by the provision of salary, bonuses, transportation money, meal money, housing facilities, and so on.

Menurut Gunawan, dkk (2020), Indikator motivasi kerja antara lain adalah sebagai berikut:

1. The need for security.
2. Social needs.
3. The need for appreciation.
4. The need for self-actualization.
5. The need for self-actualization.

THEORY.

The Influence of Communication on Motivation.

Based on research conducted by Risky Anis Safitri, Baby Taszya Risaldi, and Malinda Oktaviani (2019) entitled *The Influence of Internal Organizational Communication on the Work Motivation of Employees*

of the Public Relations Bureau of the Ministry of Industry, the following research results were obtained with a value (r) of 0.748, indicating a strong positive relationship. The contribution of internal communication to employee work motivation is 56%, with the remaining 44% influenced by variables not studied in this research.

The Influence of Job Characteristics on Motivation.

Based on research conducted by Alden Nelson, Jevie Lim, and Agustinus Setyawan (2022) entitled Analysis of the Influence of Job Characteristics on Employee Performance Through Employee Motivation Mediation in Manufacturing Industry Employees in Batam, the following research results were obtained, which identified a significant relationship between all variables, so that all hypotheses could also be accepted. This study also recommends that companies give greater consideration to employee job characteristics to enhance employee motivation, thereby achieving optimal employee performance and meeting company targets.

The Influence of Communication on Performance

Based on research conducted by Didi Wandu, Suhroji Adha, and Iyah Asriyah (2019) titled "The Influence of Communication on Employee Performance at the Regional Disaster Management Agency (BPBD) of Banten Province", the following research results were obtained, indicating that communication has a positive and significant influence on the performance of BPBD employees in Banten Province, with a calculated t-value of 8.721 and a significance level of 0.000. Meanwhile, the coefficient of determination (R²) obtained was 0.481, meaning that 48.1% of the performance variable can be explained by the communication variable, with the remainder explained by other variables.

The Influence of Job Characteristics on Performance.

Based on research conducted by Dayat IKhsan Hajati, Dwi Wahyu Artiningsih, and Hj. Nurul Wahyuni (2018) entitled The Influence of Individual Characteristics, Job Characteristics, and Organizational Characteristics on Employee Performance (A Study at Kotabaru Polytechnic), the following research findings were obtained, indicating that individual characteristics have a non-significant influence on employee performance partially, with an influence of 21.9%, job characteristics have a significant influence on employee performance partially with an influence of 38.8%, organizational characteristics have a significant influence on employee performance partially with an influence of 43.3%, individual characteristics, job characteristics, and organizational characteristics have a significant influence on employee performance simultaneously with a simultaneous influence of 35.3%.

The Influence of Motivation on Performance.

Based on research conducted by Dimas Novianto Rasetyo (2019) entitled The Influence of Work Motivation, Work Environment, Leadership, and Work Culture on Employee Performance at the Transportation Department of Gresik Regency, the research results based on multiple linear regression prove that work motivation, work environment, leadership, and work culture partially have a significant influence on employee performance at the Transportation Department of Gresik Regency. These results can be interpreted as meaning that work motivation, work environment, leadership, and work culture influence employee performance.

RESULTS. This research employs data analysis techniques using quantitative data processed with SPSS version 25 software, t-test, Sobel test, and path analysis.

Table 1. Results of t-Test for Sub Model I

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	18,430	.870		21,188	.000
	Communication	.150	.037	.472	4,069	.000
	Job Characteristics	.066	.027	.286	2,471	.017

a. Dependent Variable: Motivation

Source: authors' own elaboration

In the table, the t-statistic test is obtained, as follows:

1. Communication variable (X1) with a t-count value (4.069) > t-table (1.673) with a significance probability level (Sig) of 0.000 (< 0.05). This shows that Communication has a significant effect on the Motivation variable.

2. Job Characteristics variable (X2) with a t-count value (2.471) > t-table (1.673) with a significance probability level (Sig) of 0.017 (< 0.05). This shows that Job Characteristics have a significant effect on the Motivation variable.

Thus, the path analysis equation can be formulated as follows:

$$Z = 18.430 + 0.150 X1 + 0.066 X2$$

The meaning of this path analysis equation model is as follows:

1. The constant value of 18.430 indicates that if the independent variables, Communication (X1) and Job Characteristics (X2), are both zero, then Motivation (Z) is 18.430.

2. The regression coefficient value of $X_1 = 0.150$ indicates that if Communication increases by 100%, it will increase Motivation by 15.0%.

3. The regression coefficient value of $X_2 = 0.066$ indicates that if Job Characteristics increase by 100%, it will increase Motivation by 6.6%.

Referring to the regression output of Sub Model I, it can be seen that the significance probability (Sig) values of the two variables, namely Communication

(X_1) = 0.000 and Job Characteristics (X_2) = 0.017. These results conclude that in Sub Model I regression, the Communication variable (X_1) has a significant effect on Motivation (Z), and the Job Characteristics variable (X_2) has a significant effect on Motivation (Z).

The value of R^2 or R-square shown in the following table.

Table 2. Summary of Model Testing Results for Sub-Model I

Model Summary				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.403a	.163	.139	1,041

Source: authors' own elaboration

The data above shows that the contribution or contribution of the influence of the Communication variable (X_1) and Job Characteristics (X_2) to the Motivation variable (Z) is 25.4%, while the remaining

74.6% is the contribution of other variables not included in the research. Meanwhile, the value of $\hat{\epsilon}_1$ can be found using the formula $\hat{\epsilon}_1 = \sqrt{1-0.254} = 0.8637$.

Table 3. Results of t-Test for Sub Model II

Coefficientsa						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	30,944	3.401		9,099	.000
	Communication	.134	.054	.326	2.473	.017
	Job Characteristics	.090	.036	.303	2.486	.016
	Motivation	.474	.174	.368	2,718	.009

Source: authors' own elaboration

In the table, the t-statistic test is obtained, as follows:

1. Communication variable (X_1) has a t-count value (2.473) > t-table (1.674) with a significance probability level (Sig) of 0.017 (< 0.05). This shows that Communication has a significant effect on the Performance variable.

2. Job Characteristics variable (X_2) has a t-count value (2.486) > t-table (1.674) with a significance probability level (Sig) of 0.016 (< 0.05). This shows that Job Characteristics have a significant effect on the Performance variable.

3. The Motivation variable (Z) has a t-count value (2.718) > t-table (1.674) with a significance probability level (Sig) of 0.009 (< 0.05). This shows that Motivation has a significant effect on the Performance variable.

Thus, the path analysis equation can be formulated as follows:

$$Y = 30.944 + 0.134X_1 + 0.090X_2 + 0.474Z$$

The meaning of this path analysis equation model is as follows:

1. The constant value of 30.944 indicates that if the independent variables—Communication (X_1), Job

Characteristics (X_2), and Motivation (Z)—are all zero, then Performance (Y) is 30.944.

2. The regression coefficient value of $X_1 = 0.134$ indicates that if Communication increases by 100%, it will increase Performance by 13.4%.

3. The regression coefficient value of $X_2 = 0.090$ indicates that if Job Characteristics increase by 100%, Performance will increase by 9.0%.

4. The regression coefficient value of $Z = 0.474$ indicates that if Motivation increases by 100%, Performance will increase by 47.4%.

Referring to the regression output of Sub Model II, it can be seen that the significance probability (Sig) value of the Communication variable (X_1) is 0.017, the Job Characteristics variable (X_2) is 0.016, and the Motivation variable (Z) is 0.009. These results conclude that in Sub Model II regression, the Communication variable (X_1) has a significant effect on Performance (Y), the Job Characteristics variable (X_2) has a significant effect on Performance (Y), and the Motivation variable (Z) has a significant effect on Performance (Y).

The value of R^2 or R-square shown in the following table.

Table 4. Summary of Model Testing Results for Sub-Model II

Model Summary				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.636	.405	.379	.959

Source: authors' own elaboration

The data above shows that the contribution or contribution of the influence of the Communication variable (X1), Job Characteristics (X2) and Motivation (Z) to the Performance variable (Y) is 25.9%, while the

remaining 74.1% is the contribution of other variables not included in the research. Meanwhile, the value of ξ_1 can be found using the formula $\xi_1 = \sqrt{1-0.259} = 0.8608$.

Table 5. Results of t-Test for Sub Model II

Variables	Unstandardized	Std. Error	Test Statistics	Std. Error	P-Value
Communication to Motivation	0.150 (a)	0.037 (Sa)	2,261	0.031	0.023
Motivation for Performance	0.474 (b)	0.174 (Sb)			
Job Characteristics on Motivation	0.066 (a)	0.027 (Sa)	2,019	0.017	0.048
Motivation for Performance	0.474 (b)	0.174 (Sb)			

Source: authors' own elaboration

From the table above, the statistical test value of the influence of Communication on Performance through Motivation as an intervening variable has a statistical test value of $2.261 > 1.96$ with a significance of $0.023 < 0.05$, which means that Hypothesis 6 is accepted where Motivation is able to mediate the influence of Communication on Performance. The statistical test value of the influence of Job Characteristics on Performance through Motivation as an intervening variable has a statistical test value of $2.019 > 1.96$ with a significance of $0.048 < 0.05$, which means that Hypothesis 7 is accepted where Motivation is able to mediate the influence of Job Characteristics on Performance.

Conclusions

Based on the results of research and discussion conducted by researchers regarding the influence of Communication and Job Characteristics on Employee Performance at the Regional Revenue Agency of the Regency through Motivation as an intervening variable, the following conclusions can be drawn:

1. Communication influences motivation In Badan Pendapatan Daerah Kabupaten Labuhan Batu
2. Job Characteristics Influence Motivation In Badan Pendapatan Daerah Kabupaten Labuhan Batu
3. Communication influences performance In Badan Pendapatan Daerah Kabupaten Labuhan Batu

4. Job Characteristics Influence Performance In Badan Pendapatan Daerah Kabupaten Labuhan Batu

5. Motivation influences performance In Badan Pendapatan Daerah Kabupaten Labuhan Batu

6. Communication influences performance at the Regional Revenue Agency of Labuhanbatu Regency through motivation as an intervening variable.

7. Job Characteristics Influence Performance at the Regional Revenue Agency of Labuhanbatu Regency through Motivation as an intervening variable.

Suggestions

1. The Regional Revenue Agency of Labuhanbatu Regency should increase the awareness and willingness of employees to comply with applicable laws and regulations.

2. The Regional Revenue Agency of Labuhanbatu Regency should create an effective atmosphere and communication in the workplace so that changes in actions for the better can be felt.

3. The Regional Revenue Agency of Labuhanbatu Regency needs to encourage employees to be willing to use their own work methods and schedule their own time.

4. The Regional Revenue Agency of Labuhanbatu Regency needs to encourage the willingness of employees to be willing and able to complete challenging work by deploying their full potential.

Abstract

This research aims to determine whether Communication and Job Characteristics affect Performance through Motivation as an intervening variable on employees of the Regional Revenue Agency of Labuhanbatu Regency. The research was conducted on permanent employees (PNS) at the Regional Revenue Agency of Labuhanbatu Regency. The population in this research was 57 people. Because the population is small, the sampling technique in this research was a saturated sample with a sample size of 57 people.

The data collection technique used was primary data in the form of questionnaires and secondary data obtained through documentation studies. The data analysis technique used quantitative data processed with the SPSS version 25 program, namely the t-test, Sobel test and path analysis. The results obtained in this research indicate 1) there is a positive and significant influence between Communication on Motivation, 2) there is a positive and

significant influence between Job Characteristics on Motivation, 3) there is a positive and significant influence between Communication on Performance, 4) there is a positive and significant influence between Job Characteristics on Performance, 5) there is a positive and significant influence between Motivation on Performance, 6) There is a positive and significant influence between Communication on Performance through Motivation as an intervening variable, 7) There is a positive and significant influence between Job Characteristics on Performance through Motivation as an intervening variable.

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